

Combine Application of Reversible Watermarking Technique and RSA Algorithm to Verify Ownership of Digital Images: A Hybrid Image Restoration Approach

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Abstract

Recently reversible watermarking has lots of interest among data hiding techniques due to the property of complete restoration of original ground truth image from watermarked image without altering the original features. And these features are more useful for medical and military images, as these kinds of images are very sensitive to loss of little bits of information. So, we proposed a novel image restoration method. The proposed restoration scheme is a combination of Modified reversible watermarking algorithm and RSA algorithm. In this scheme the resultant watermarked image will be encrypted by RSA algorithm. For execution of RSA algorithm the watermarked image converted into 2-D array of bytes. The 2-D array of bytes is a matrix of discrete values. For encryption of these matrix values, randomly choose two large numbers say P and Q, out of n-numbers of discrete values, which are co-prime to each other. Take the product of 'P' and 'Q' and store it on 'n', i.e. $n = p \times q$, in such a that the value of n must be within the length of grayscale intensity values. Then calculate product of two co-prime numbers by reducing 1 in iteratively and store that product in Φ , i.e. $\Phi = (p - 1) \times (q - 1)$. For each iteration value of Φ choose an encryption exponent e and its value must satisfy $1 < e < \Phi$ and $\gcd(e, \Phi) = 1$. On the other hand for decryption of encrypted values, select a decryption exponent 'd' such that it must satisfy $1 < d < \Phi$ and $e \times d = 1 \pmod{\Phi}$. To avoid unauthentic access the key pairs: public key (n, e) and private or secret key (n, d) will be kept as secret. Here the decrypted image will be go through AMC algorithm for extraction of watermark image, as reversely applying of encryption process. Therefore it is an approach of image restoration technique. The performance matrix include, higher in capacity and quality with respect to number of Pixel changing rate (NPCR or NCPR) and unified averaged changed intensity (UACI) values, than traditional reversible watermarking techniques. It aims to enhance human visibility and accurately represent the image of the original scene, i.e. restoration of a degraded image to its original content and quality. So, the proposed algorithm is a two-way locking mechanism to verify ownership.

Keywords-Embedding, Medical images, NPCR, Restoration, Reversible watermarking, RSA, Ownership, UACI.

1. INTRODUCTION

Digital images are easy to copy, crop and cut in the digital world without permission of ownership, which is the violation of intellectual property right. So, to increase the strength of intellectual property right, it needs to protect copyright of digital images. Copyright protections are achieved through different data hiding techniques and digital watermarking is one of them. Digital image watermarking is the process of data hiding. It provides authenticity, originality, and ownership of digital images. Some of the owners use trade mark as the watermark for embedding with their protected images and the resulting image is called as watermarked image. The transmitted watermarked image over any channel or transmission media is called suspected image. The suspected image may be corrupted due to some unintentional natural hazards or by some intentional third-party hackers or attackers. On the other hand, the retrieved result will find out the ownership of suspected image. In general, one good watermarking scheme should meet the following requirements [1].

A. Robustness

Robustness is the property of noise payload bearing capacity of any watermarking algorithm. So, every watermarking algorithm should have resistance capacity to avoid malevolent attack and destruction of embedded watermark by third party intentional or unintentional hackers to loss ownership. For example, the watermarked image will be compressed before transmission or being stored in any media. So, the watermarked image should survive in legitimate uses like lossy compression, image type conversion, resampling of images and other non-malevolent operations. The robust watermarking algorithm provides guarantees to recognize retrieved watermark, subject to image quality not being hampered severely. If the developed watermark algorithm is not strong enough or robust, the embedded watermark can be easily removed even in judicial proceeding, making it unproven. So, a good watermarking algorithm should have resistance against addition of noises, filtering operations and geometric transformations like scaling, translations, and rotations.

B. Imperceptibility

The perceptibility is the property of visibility of watermark in the cover image, which is just like a noise and it can be removed through denoising process. Due to two important reasons imperceptibility of cover media has occurred after adding of watermark data. In first, to avoid tampering risk due to visibility and in second, to maintain the quality between original cover image and extracted cover image from watermarked image, i.e., if the embedded watermark data is drastically distorted then retrieved value will be lost. As a result, the imperceptibility can be defined as the ratio of visual quality between the watermarked image and the original ground truth cover image that was recovered.

C. Embedding and Extracting

The embedded watermark should be simply and safely extracted by the owner, such that the embedding process and extracting process ought to be restricted in reasonable range. The poor embedding algorithm seriously affect the watermarked image quality. The poor embedding process entices the devotion of hackers or attackers, which drastically degrade the retrieving value.

Recently reversible watermarking is a unique type of digital watermarking that has gained a lot of attention for copyright protection. This watermarking scheme protects copyright by putting a watermark symbol into the original cover image and recovers the original cover image from suspected one. When the assigned watermark and the retrieved watermark are compared, ownership can be ascertained. Like conventional watermarking methods, the reversible watermarking method must be resilient to both intentional and unintentional attacks. They also need to be undetectable to prevent attacks and value loss. The reversible watermarking must meet the same characteristics as conventional watermarking, including resilience, imperceptibility, and easy embedding and retrieval.

Besides above requirements, reversible watermarking must meet following two more requirements.

- *Blind*

Certain traditional watermarking methods need the assistance of original cover image in order to extract the embedded watermarking image. On the other hand, with reversible watermarking, we may easily remove the watermark and the original cover image revert back directly. For this reason, the original image is not necessary for the recovery process when using reversible watermarking scheme. So, it is blind.

- *Better Embedding Capacity*

The embedding capacity refers to the maximum amount of information that may be stored or encoded in a given space. Reversible watermarking method needs the embedding of both recovery information and watermark information into the original image, resulting in a significantly higher embedding capacity compared to the conventional watermarking methods. Since a very low embedding capacity could compromise the accuracy of both the recovered image and retrieved watermark, poor embedding capacity is avoided to ensure accurate watermark retrieval and image recovery.

Fig. 1 Conventional Watermarking Scheme Flow Chart

Fig. 2 Reversible Watermarking Scheme Flow chart

Fig. 3 General Architecture of Reversible Watermarking Scheme

The Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 show the methodology of both conventional watermarking and reversible watermarking systems respectively, using flowcharts representation. The methodology of conventional watermarking and reversible watermarking have similarities, with the exception that reversible watermarking includes an additional capability to restore original cover image from the suspected image. The suspected image is one form of watermarked image. The RSA encryption is applied over watermarked image. The encrypted image looks like a noise image, which is very difficult to attack intentionally or non-intentionally. So, reversible watermarking is particularly well-suited for applications which need high-quality images like medical and military imagery. Whereas Fig. 3 shows the architecture and internal execution of reversible watermarking scheme.

Furthermore, digital watermarking is typically associated with two research areas: first one is data hiding [2], often known as steganography, and second one is image authentication [3]. Fundamental requirements of reversible watermarking are robustness, imperceptibility, large embedding capacity, easy embedding & retrieval process and blindness. Furthermore, stated as the system allowing one to retrieve the original image from the embedded image are called as reversible data hiding method and reversible image authentication model. This study focuses on methods for digital images because, currently maximum reversible watermarking techniques are developed for digital images.

So far, there have been various proposed reversible watermarking techniques [4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21]. Our proposed reversible watermarking model consists of five algorithms, as follows:

Algorithm 1: Generation of Quick Response code for Patient Information.

Algorithm 2: Implementations of embedding technique using Algebraic Mean Compression process, called watermarked image.

Algorithm 3: Encrypt the transmitted watermarked image using RSA algorithm, called suspected image.

Algorithm 4: Decrypt the suspected image at receiver side to get watermarked image.

Algorithm 5: Implementations of retrieving technique using Algebraic Mean Decompression process for retrieval of original image.

The key contributions of this research paper, especially beyond what is presented in its preliminary conference publication [21] are:

- 1) We conduct a thorough analysis of the security concerns associated with reversible watermarking, which include resistance to both intentional and unintentional attacks, high-capability and low-distortion data-embedding, imperceptibility, and protection of copyright, efficiency manipulation of embedding process, and visual quality manipulation of retrieved cover image and watermarked image. So, we proposed "A Modified Framework for Reversible Digital Image Watermarking".

- 2) But, in our extension work, the suggested strategy implements a two-way locking mechanism utilizing novel modified watermarking technique and RSA encryption algorithm to avoid intentional and unintentional attack.
- 3) The post-decryption regime that is susceptible to intellectual property theft and piracy is analyzed, by using key space analysis and plaintext analysis. The preventative measures are suggested in order to thwart any potential future threats.

2. RELATED WORK

In the perspectives of medical image information security and authentication identification, watermarking technique and reverse watermarking technique have been the subject of numerous research efforts. For Ultra Sound (US) DICOM images Zain et al. suggested spatial domain watermarking [23]. Their proposed model has four stages. Beginning with a rectangle shape, the region of interest (ROI) is removed from the zone that is not of interest (RONI). The next step is for the hash function to determine the hash value of the image. The final bit of RONI is the hash value, which is the least significant bit. In regards to DICOM images Qershi, et al. introduced a ROI based hybrid architecture for watermarking model to achieve both authentication and data concealment [24]. By using their suggested method, the ROI and RONI region of DICOM cover image, are separated completely from each other. Next, the reversible difference expansion method is used to embed patient data at the area of ROI. By using trustworthy DWT transform method, the RONI area incorporated with tamper detection and recovery data. Reza et al. [25] proposed a model for RONI areas. In this model they included patient data and authentication watermark in the areas of RONI. For their embedding method they designed hybrid transform named DWT-SVD by using DWT transform and SVD decomposition procedures.

But again, the reversible watermarking approach, discusses several methods that are now being utilized for the information extraction from the embedded media as well as the hidden information.

There was no reversible data embedding methodology before 1994 era. In the year 1994, the Barton designed a patent, with an exception. In Barton method, a bit string is compressed within a data block and overplayed bits are added to the string. In order to retrieve original image without loss of information, first recreate the payload by subtracting the payload from embedded image [26]. Developing a high-capacity, reversible data-embedding scheme by utilizing the embedded message status on pixels. There are two reversible approaches for data-embedding such as JPEG lossy image formats [27] and theoretical capacity limits based on lossless data compression [28]. Additionally, except these two-compression model another one is viable code architecture, which provides higher embedding capacity than JPEG lossy image format and lower embedding capacity than lossless data compression [29]. Out of above three techniques, the quantization residue compressions data-embedding scheme has properties of reversibility, high-capability and low-distortion data-embedding, which has been implemented by us in this proposed methodology.

In recent years, there are variety of reversible watermarking techniques. Most of these techniques have used lossless compression to extract image blocks for the watermark application. For example, the difference expansion [30] method finds expandable coefficients which give an additional bit for watermark operations.

So, the reversible watermark can be characterized as: It is a unique type of digital watermarking that has gained a lot of attention in recent years. By adding the designated watermark to the original image, it not only offers copyright protection, but it also has the ability to extract the original from the allegedly tampered with image. Through a comparison between the assigned and retrieved watermarks, ownership can be ascertained. Reversible watermarking methods, like conventional ones, must be resilient to both purposeful and inadvertent attacks. They also need to be undetectable to prevent attacks and value loss. Consequently, all requirements of conventional watermarking, including robustness, imperceptibility, and ease of embedding and retrieval, must also be met by reversible watermarking.

3. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Reversible watermarking techniques have a lot of potential, even though they are still in early stages of development. When it comes to applications that require high-quality images for analysis, such as medical imaging systems and military imaging systems, reversible watermarking is particularly suitable for those kinds of applications. Reversible watermarking is one of more helpful spatial approach used to improve robustness. Reversible watermarking is technique used to apply watermarks without causing any deformation. In this research, our proposed model consists of 5 algorithms. The patient's primary data will transform into a Quick Response (QR) code in algorithm 1. Algorithm 2 will form a watermarked image by employing a novel algebraic compression approach to embed the watermark image with a ground truth cover image. To prevent unauthorized access, the algorithm 3 encrypts the watermarked image during transmission by using RSA algorithm. The encrypted watermarked image is called as suspected image. Decrypt the suspected image in algorithm 4 to obtain the watermarked version of the image. The algorithm 5 perform retrieving process by utilizing the algebraic mean decomposition method, get the original image following decryption.

4. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

A modified and improved framework, proposed for reversible digital image watermarking scheme. By using this procedure, the input cover image divided into 4×4 blocks. The watermark image will add with cover image in order to form watermarked image, by using L-level scalar quantization. The watermark images are of any logo or trade mark symbols or may be of any kind of noises like white gaussian noises. The L-level scalar quantization divides the cover image into two matrices: one is quotient matrix and other one is remainder matrix. The remainder matrix compresses by using novel mean algebraic method in order to

add watermark image. And the resultant image is called watermarked image. The watermarked image will send to receiver through a transmission media or channel. To avoid unauthorized asses during transmission, the RSA encryption technique will apply for encrypted transmission. The encrypted transmitted image is called suspected image. The suspected image will be decrypted in order to get watermarked image. On the receiver side the reverse L-level Scalar quantization will apply for decompression and retrieval of watermark and original cover image.

Reversible digital image watermarking algorithms for JPEG 2000 compression are included in the proposed scheme. The proposed reversible watermarking's designing criteria have been defined as architecture sub-modules. Using MATLAB and JAVA programming, a software reference model for reversible watermarking sub-modules is created based on the stated architecture and algorithms. The simulation of the reversible watermarking top module yields the desired results. The diagram that follows in Fig.- 4 explains the sequential steps involved in the execution of sub-modules for the proposed reversible digital image watermarking.

Fig. 4 Execution Flow Diagram of submodules of Proposed Reversible Watermarking Model

A. Proposed Model Algorithms and Flow Diagram

The modified proposed reversible watermarking model consists of four algorithms, which are described in details as follows.

Algorithm 1: QR Code generation submodule

1. Store patient's details i.e. Patient Name, Department, Gender and Age in a .txt file.
2. Create object(s) for following classes

```
File obj=new File("data.txt");
FileReader frd=new FileReader(obj);
BufferedReader brd = new BufferedReader(frd);
String str;
```
3. Generate watermark image by converting .txt file to .png image file as follows.

```

while((str=brd.readLine())!=null)
{
String data[]=str.split("\t");
String qrdata="Department: "+data[0]+" \n "+" Patient Name: "+data[1] ]+"\n"+"Gender: "+data[2];+"\n"+"Age: "+data[3];

String path = data[0]+"_QR.png";
String charset = "UTF-8"; //Encoding charset to be used
Map<EncodeHintType, ErrorCorrectionLevel> hashMap = new HashMap<EncodeHintType, ErrorCorrectionLevel>();
hashMap.put(EncodeHintType.ERROR_CORRECTION, ErrorCorrectionLevel.L);
generateQRcode(qrdata, path, charset, hashMap, 200, 200);//Increase or decrease height and width accordingly
System.out.println(data[0]+"_QR Code created successfully."); //prints if the QR code is generated
}
}
4. Invoke frd.close(); method to deallocate the main memory

```

Execution Flow Diagram:

Fig. 5 Execution Flow Diagram of QR code generation algorithm

Algorithm 2: Watermarked image generation submodule

Embedding Process:

1. Get the grayscale ground truth cover image $c(i, j)$ and use it as input.
2. Make 4 X 4 blocks of equal sections out of the entire cover image $c(i, j)$.
3. Calculate the quotient matrix $Q_L(x)$ and remainder matrix $R_L(x)$ for each pixel in terms of a 4x4 matrix by applying L-level scalar quantization to each pixel value x . For these, the formula is as follows:

$$Q_L(x) = \lfloor x/L \rfloor \text{ and } R_L(x) = x \% L$$

4. Apply compression to the remainder matrix $R_L(x)$. Carrying out an algebraic mean operation on neighboring elements of each column with respect to the floor function gets the matrix into the 3x4 dimension. For these, the formula is as follows:

$$R_{comp}(x) = \lfloor (x + y)/2 \rfloor,$$

where (x, y) are the adjacent pixel belongs to same column C_i

5. To reform 4×4 matrix from 3×4 matrix, embed QR code as watermark in $R_{comp}(x)$ matrix. The reformed 4×4 matrix say $R_{embd}(x)$.

6. Perform reversely L-level Scalar quantization to obtained watermarked image $w(i, j)$ over quotient matrix $Q_L(x)$, L-level Scalar Quantization L and embedded matrix $R_{embd}(x)$. For these the formula is as follows:

$$w(i, j) = L \times Q_L(x) + R_{embd}(x)$$

Execution Flow Diagram:

Fig. 6 Execution Flow Diagram of Watermark Embedding Process

Algorithm 3: Suspected image generation submodule using RSA encryption

Key Generation Algorithm

1. Convert the produced watermarked image $w(i, j)$ into a two-dimensional array of bytes or a matrix of discrete values.
2. Determine two large random co-primes or approximately of equal size of pixel intensity values p and q so that the product $p \times q$ falls within the necessary bit length of grayscale intensity values.
3. Calculate $n = p \times q$ and $\Phi = (p - 1) \times (q - 1)$.
4. select a number e as public exponent or encryption exponent from set of integers \hat{I} , where $1 < e < \Phi$ such that greatest common divisor (gcd) of e and Φ will be 1 i.e. $\text{gcd}(e, \Phi) = 1$.
5. select a number d as secret exponent or decryption exponent from set of integers \hat{I} , where $1 < d < \Phi$ such that product of e and d will be 1 mod Φ i.e. $e \times d = 1(\text{mod } \Phi)$
6. To avoid unauthentic access the key pairs: public key (n, e) and private or secret key (n, d) will be kept as secret.

Execution Flow Diagram:

Fig. 7 Execution Flow Diagram of Key generation of Encryption Process

Encryption Algorithm:

1. Convert the produced watermarked image $w(i, j)$ with of size $M \times N$, into a two-dimensional array of bytes or a matrix of discrete values.
2. Get the recipient's public key (n, e)

3. Extract information entropy E of image $w(i, j)$ having size $M \times N$, and it is defined as

$$E = - \sum_{i=0}^{M \times N} p \log_2^p$$

Where, p is the probability of particular intensity values of a pixel has occurred randomly. For example, for a grayscale image p is the probability of random numbers between $0 \dots, 255$.

4. calculate sum of pixel intensity value of image $w(i, j)$ having size $M \times N$, and it is defined as

$$sum_{px} = \sum_{\substack{i=0 \\ j=0}}^{M \times N} w(i, j)$$

and produces two random numbers r1 and r2.

5. Generate three plain messages α , β and γ using parametric transformation function (PTF), and it is defined as

$$\begin{cases} \alpha = \text{mod}(\lfloor (E + r_2) \times e^{r_2} \rfloor, n) \\ \beta = \text{mod}(sum_{px}, n) \\ \gamma = \text{mod}(r_1, n) \end{cases}$$

6. Apply the RSA encryption over plane messages α , β and γ and compute corresponding cipher text α' , β' and γ' as

$$\begin{cases} \alpha' = \alpha^e \text{ mod } n \\ \beta' = \beta^e \text{ mod } n \\ \gamma' = \gamma^e \text{ mod } n \end{cases}$$

7. Step 6 will continue until to produce a sequence of processing of $\alpha^{(i,j)}$, $\beta^{(i,j)}$ and $\gamma^{(i,j)}$

8. The first M values of sequences of $\alpha^{(i,j)}$, $\beta^{(i,j)}$ and $\gamma^{(i,j)}$ of odd positions, put in horizontal direction, and the first N values of sequences $\alpha^{(i,j)}$, $\beta^{(i,j)}$ and $\gamma^{(i,j)}$ of even positions put in vertical direction, which results a new image $w'(i, j)$, called Cipher Image.

9. Send cypher image $w'(i, j)$, to the receiver.

Execution Flow Diagram:

Fig. 8 Execution Flow Diagram of Encryption Process

Decryption Algorithm:

The following execution diagram illustrates how the receiver utilizes his private key (n, d) to carry out the decryption process, which is identical to the encryption phases but is done in reverse order.

Fig. 9 Flowchart of decryption process at receiver end

Remark: The specifics of the implementation approach will not be addressed here, as the explanation of the decryption process for cipher images mirrors the encryption process and is uncomplicated. The technique for detailed implementations will not be addressed here.

Algorithm 5: Watermarked image extraction submodule

Extracting Process:

1. Consider Watermarked image $w(i, j)$ which was obtained from the embedding procedure, and utilize it as the input.
2. Calculate the quotient matrix $Q_{Lr}(x)$ and remainder matrix $R_{Lr}(x)$ for each pixel in terms of a 4×4 matrix by applying L-level scalar quantization to each pixel value x of watermarked image $w(i, j)$. For these, the formula is as follows:
 $Q_{Lr}(x) = \lfloor x/L \rfloor$ and $R_{Lr}(x) = x \% L$
3. To extract QR code or reverse watermark image $w_r(i, j)$ and from $R_{Lr}(x)$, decompress the $R_{Lr}(x)$. For these, the formula is as follows:

$R_{Dcomp}(x) = \lfloor (x + y)/2 \rfloor$, where (x, y) are the adjacent pixel belongs to same column C_i of $w(i, j)$. and $w_r(i, j) = \sum_{i=0}^{L-1} L^i \times R_{Lr}(x)$, here $R_{Lr}(x)$ is a matrix of order 1×4 .

4. To extract reverse cover image $c_r(i, j)$ perform the process as $c_r(i, j) = L \times Q_{Lr}(x) + R_{Dcomp}(x)$

Execution Flow Diagram:

Fig. 10 Execution Flow Diagram of Cover Image and Watermark Extracting Process

5. SIMULATION RESULT

This section shows image encryption and decryption simulation results. In these experimental results the retrieved images are the decrypted images. The proposed algorithm and its simulation results are run on a desktop with an Intel(R) Core (TM) i3-10110U CPU @ 2.10GHz 2.50 GHz and 8 GB RAM. All studies and procedures are conducted using MATLAB (Version R2020A) and java programming languages. In this experimental work, e, n, α', β' and γ' are taken as the public keys and the private key is determined as d . Stochastically assign the values $e=295n=1771073$ and $d=1396711$. The Fig. 11 represents the encryption and decryption results for both grayscale as well as color images. From the figure it can be seen that all the encrypted images are seen without useful information like the noisy-images, whereas the decrypted images are recovered as well. All the images are taken from MURAV1.1 dataset of Stanford University Medical School, California, USA and EPFL RGB-NIR dataset having IHS images. There are different images having different pixels, out of them we have taken only 256×256 pixels

and 512×512 pixels images that make up the resolution of the selected image. Every image contains a patient's data that conveys the patient's admitted department, name, gender, and age.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

(g)

(h)

(i)

(j)

(k)

(l)

(m)

(n)

(o)

(p)

Fig.11 Encryption and Decryption Simulation results.

The 1st column of Fig. 11 are the original cover images, 2nd column are the watermark images, third column images are the Encrypted images and 4th column images are the decrypted images. The images of First three row are of 512 X 512-pixel sizes where are as the images of last three rows are of 256 X 256-pixel sizes. The images of all rows are the grayscale images except last row images. The last row images are RGB color images.

In the simulation result, we got the proposed model is not working for RGB color images. When it decrypted the RSA encrypted form of input color image, the output retrieval decrypted image takes the form of grayscale image with loss of some information. The loss of information is the serious issue for medical and military image analysis.

6. ANALYSIS OF DIFFERENT SECURITY ISSUES

In generally, the security of RSA algorithm based on the factoring problem. The factoring problem is the finding out two large numbers, which are used for key generation process. During the key generation process, when key length is higher factoring the product of two large prime numbers is more difficult. Except these issues, other issues are discussed as follows.

A. Analysis of Key Space

Key space refers to the unbounded collection of all potential keys for an encryption method. A larger key space range typically serves as a deterrent against brute-force attacks. Thus, algorithms with a greater key space range exhibit more efficiency in countering any given attack. This work utilizes the information entropy E , the sum of pixel intensity values sum_{px} of the plane image $w(i, j)$, and two random numbers $r1$ and $r2$ to generate initial keys for the encryption scheme. As a result, these keys serve as an intermediary in determining the key spacing size. For example, define a floating-point number with precise is set as 10^{-15} then key Space reaches to size of $1015 \times 1015 \times 1015 = 1045 \cong 2149$. Since the level of key volume needs to be greater than equals to 2100 in order to withstand exhaustive attacks [31]. So, our proposed encrypted scheme effectively resists brute-force attack.

B. Analysis of Sensitivity

In the context of image cryptography, there are two methods: key sensitivity and plain text sensitivity that are typically utilized when addressing the issue of sensitivity. The process of establishing how the cryptosystem responds to even minute changes in the plain text or the key is referred to as the sensitivity analysis. The encryption algorithm can produce greater security performance the higher the sensitivity. Both Quantitative and qualitative analysis are used for sensitivity analysis.

Qualitative analysis talks about visual judgement difference between two images in human eyes,

whereas quantitative analysis talks about numerical data difference between two images by using numerical methods such as number of changing pixel rate (NPCR) and unified averaged changed intensity (UACI). UACI is a metric for the average number of intensities of change, whereas NPCR is a metric for the number of pixels that have changed. These metrics are calculated using the following equation:

$$\begin{cases} NPCR(I_1, I_2) = \sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{D(i, j)}{MN} \times 100\% \\ UACI(I_1, I_2) = \sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{I_1(i, j) - I_2(i, j)}{255 \times MN} \times 100\% \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Here, $I_1(i, j)$ and $I_2(i, j)$ are two images and $D(i, j)$ is defined as follows.

$$D(i, j) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } I_1(i, j) = I_2(i, j) \\ 1, & \text{if } I_1(i, j) \neq I_2(i, j) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The ideal value of NPCR is 99.6094% and UACI is 33.4635% [32].

C. Key Sensitivity Analysis

Key sensitivity includes sensitivity of both encryption and decryption key sensitivity. The objective of this study is to capture grayscale images with dimensions of 128×128 pixels, 256×256 pixels, and 512×512 pixels. The images undergo testing with a transformation of 10-15 in each key to determine the NPCR and UACI values. These values are then compared with the ideal values of NPCR and UACI as shown in the tables below.

TABLE 1: ENCRYPTED KEY SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

Sl. No.	Image	Size	NPCR	UACI
1	Chest X-ray	256 × 256 pixels	99.6154 %	33.4176 %
2	House	256 × 256 pixels	99.6014 %	33.5016 %
3	Mandrill	256 × 256 pixels	99.6123 %	33.4252 %
4	Butterfly	128 × 128 pixels	99.6198 %	33.5246 %
5	Lena	256 × 256 pixels	99.6012 %	33.5117 %
6	RGB Tower	512 × 512 pixels	97.5053 %	32.0012 %

The suggested model produces fairly similar results for NPCR and UACI values when compared to ideal values, as can be seen from the above table. Furthermore, it is recognized that the suggested model performs appallingly poorly for RGB color images

D. Graphical Representation:

Fig. 12 Bar chart representation of NPCR values comparison

Fig. 13 Pie chart representation of NPCR values comparison

It is evident from the graphical representations above that, with the exception of RGB tower color images, the calculated NPCR values of the suggested model are extremely close to the ideal NPCR values of all images.

Fig. 14 Bar chart representation of UACI values comparison

Fig. 15 Pie chart representation of UACI values comparison

It is evident from the graphical representations above that, with the exception of RGB tower color images, the calculated UACI values of the suggested model are extremely close to the ideal UACI values of all images.

E. Sensitivity Analysis of Plaintext

Calculating the degree between two cipher images, each of which has a single bit changed, is known as plaintext sensitivity. One must choose two random numbers, r_1 and r_2 , in order to generate two cipher images for a given plaintext image. Both known and chosen plaintext attacks can be better resisted with a high sensitivity to plaintext. A random pixel is chosen from the input image, and its value is altered by one bit to conduct the test, as demonstrated in the subsequent equation.

$$p(i, j) = \text{mod}(p(i, j) + 1, 256), \text{ where } i = 1, 2, \dots, M \text{ and } j = 1, 2, \dots, N \quad (3)$$

The evaluated values of NPCR% and UACI% are taken into analyzed the sensitivity of plaintext. As a result of the fact that our evaluated NPCR and UACI values have a very close relationship to the ideal values of NPCR% and UACI% for all grayscale images. So, our proposed approach is both highly sensitive to plaintext and performs better than its predecessor.

7. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this work, the novel Image restoration technique implemented using modified reversible watermarking algorithm and RSA asymmetric encryption process. During the compression and decompression process, watermarked image formed from original input cover image added as an intentional noise. The watermarked is encrypted by RSA encryption in order to form cipher image using parametric transformation function (PTF), for better and secure transmission. After simulation and tests, the evaluated NPCR and UACI values are extremely close to the ideal NPCR and UACI values for all grayscale images. On the other hand, RGB color images simulate poorly due to data loss. So, future research will focus on Advanced Encrypted Standard (AES) algorithm instead of RSA algorithm for finding ways to make more efficient encryption and decryption standard.

Data availability statement

All considered datasets are open-source datasets. We have cited all references of the datasets.

Note on competing interests and obligations

The authors affirm that they do not possess any identifiable conflicting financial interests or personal affiliations that may have influenced the research presented in this scholarly article.

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